

A FABRICATION AND MICRO STRUCTURAL STUDY OF AL-6061 METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The ultimate goal of the current works linked to the material characterization of manufactured Al-6061 by "stir casting method" as expanding proportion by weight and particle size of B4C improved their reinforcement impact and a unique benefit is the capacity to use many resin combinations and reinforcements particularly in the aerospace industry. In addition, SEM was used to observe the impacts of strengthened particle sizes on the composite microstructure. The finer particles will make the dislocation flow more effective and more homogeneously dispersed in the aluminum matrix. Larger particles are more prone to settling gravity and may result in matrix region reinforcement clustering and agglomeration. Composites of aluminum metal matrix.

Key words: Particle Size, microstructure, Aluminum Metal Matrix Composites, Stir Casting Technique, Reinforcement.

1. Introduction

Due to their high strength, low density, improved high refractory characteristics and damping capacities, aluminum alloy based ceramic particulate composites have been characterized as futuristic materials are preferred by technicians. (Gagandeep Singh et. al. 2019) researched Al-B4C-based metal matrix composites which could be achieved by manufactured aluminum as AMMCs with a proportion of enhanced B4C relative particle size and compressive mechanical behavior[1]. (Gagandeep Singh et al. 2019) invested the compressive strength of the B4C reinforced metal matrix composite based on Al-6061 and showed a better interfacial relationship between the matrix and the reinforced material by maintaining the smaller B4C particle size. Therefore, the contribution of the percentage of B4C is more significant than the particle size [2]. Al-6061 metal matrix composites (Shipra Verma 2018) were discovered to boost strength and weight ratio. The manufactured composite can be used for apps with light weight and high strength. Furthermore, ageing increases the strength, micro and macro-hardness of the composites manufactured. To further explore the interfacial features, the strengthened composite specimens with distinct particle sizes of Al-6061 in μm were also manufactured. It is noted that clustering was shown in the tiny particle size samples. The composites are manufactured using a straightforward and cost-effective stir casting method and the findings demonstrate that

composites have greater modulus than unreinforced alloy. Compared to the unreinforced alloy, the composites show greater maximum hardness and accelerated ageing. A 6061 AlB4C -15 percent composite demonstrates greater ultimate tensile and compressive strength relative to the peak-age Alloy. Composite comprising Al-B4C was manufactured with variable weight proportion of B4C particle size. From Scanning electron microscopy it is noted that with the rise in proportion of the strengthened particle, the homogeneous and uniform distribution of metal in the matrix of the composite material rises and, as demonstrated by the enhanced mechanical characteristics of these components, the interfacial structure bonding in this scheme is relatively powerful [3-6]. (Suresh R and M. Prasanna Kumar et. al. 2013) experimented with a linear decrease in wear rate and friction coefficient with an increase in Al-6061 weight proportion. As the sliding velocity rises, the wear rate improves. The SEM of Aluminum 6061 composites generated by the stir casting technique demonstrates that B4C and Al-6061 particles in the metal matrix are fairly uniformly distributed. The inclusion of Al-6061 and B4C particles as reinforcements enhanced tribological conduct and resulted in a decrease in the wear rate during the dry drying phase of Aluminum 6061 composites[10]. Wear parameters such as sliding range, pressure, sliding velocity of Al-6061 composite were evaluated (Pramanik. et. al. 2016). For the research of wear, a pin-on-disk wear machine was used. A disk made of steel has been used. Researched study demonstrates that the wear resistance of the composite used in this research job was much greater than that of matrix materials[8]. (Khalil et. al. 2012) evaluated the present development of strengthened composites based on bamboo fibre. The materials are used in composites because bamboo fibers were reinforced. The bamboo fiber, which is stronger than other fibers, was used as raw material in product design and used to produce viable goods of high quality[4]. The mechanical characteristics of mixed fly ash and aluminum alloy (Al-6061) were explored (H.C Anil kumar et. al. 2011). The casting stir used to process the samples. The particle size is 4-25, 45-50 and 75-100 with three composite sets being used. In this studies, the mechanical characteristics have been researched. The unreinforced Al6061 samples have also been screened for the same characteristics. The mechanical characteristics of aluminum 6061 composite were discovered to reduce by raising the size of fly ash particles [3]. The tensile behavior of hard particle-reinforced composite (Shao-Yun et. al. 2002) is primarily dependent on the type of interfacial bonding between the Al-matrix and the reinforcement. This is due to the powerful interface bond that plays a critical part in the transfer of loads from the matrix to the tough particles. In the case of heat treated alloy, due to higher strength and ductility of the Al matrix, the effective stress applied to the composite surface during wear process is less. This led to a lower inclination of the composite surface compared to the cast alloy [13]. (Soon-chal et. al. 2006) Heat therapy has not radically altered morphology, but has hardened the matrix by hardening precipitation, resulting in greater strength and hardness. The findings of countless researchers in the particle sector over the years strengthened Al-MMCs. In terms of strength, the mechanical characteristics were evaluated [12].

2. Sample Fabrication Methodology

The Stir casting process was created by preheating the billet of Al-6061 alloy using vertical muffle furnace with graphite crucible and stirring the material into the molten metal. This involves stirring the melt with ceramic B₄C 5%, 10%, 15% by weight at different levels and allowing the mixture to solidify afterwards. Usually this can be prepared using relatively standard processing facilities and can be done on a constant and semi-continuous basis. The technology is comparatively easy and low cost to manufacture the Al-MMC samples by weight of at least three parts of each sample according to the normal sample requirements [13].

Design Procedure:

3. Results & Discussion

3.1 Morphology studies

It was noted that as much research is accomplished on B₄C-based Al-MMCs compared to MgO-based Al-MMCs after the literature study. The microstructure of Al-6061 alloys and B₄C reinforcement particles is a relatively and uniformly distributed agglomeration of particle-based composites and the interface bonding between the matrix and strengthened particles is quite sharp, showing a reasonably excellent bonding of Al-MMCs by different weight percentages of morphology research. As the density rises, the MMC becomes stiffer as there is not as much room for the molecules to move around. The entanglement of the molecules also resists motion as the molecular weight rises. In addition to reducing porosity, a better particle distribution in all alumina composites was accomplished.

Figure 1. (a) At 50-mesh 5 % (wt.) of B₄C-AMMCs

Figure 1. (b) At 100- mesh 5 % (wt.) of B₄C-AMMCs.

Figure 1. (c) At 150-mesh 5 % (wt.) of B₄C –AMMCs

Figure 1. (d) At 50-mesh 5 (wt.) % of B₄C –AMMCs

Figure 1. (e) At 0% (wt.) of B4C-AMMCs

Figure 1. (f) At 0% (wt.) of B4C-AMMCs.

The size, shape and texture of the original well-structured silicon under scanning electron microscopy (Model: SEM–JSM 6600) Using secondary electron imaging mode of scanning electron microscopy, a relatively higher degree of Boron Carbide was researched. The SEM picture of the original Boron carbide particles is mostly angular at a weight of 5%. Here the angular structure of the original boron carbide was demolished and the flake-shaped particles were observed with a 15% rise in B4C weight strengthening, the final shape of the particles was mostly sub-angular and the surface morphology was rough as shown in Figure 2(a), (b), (c), (d) and (e) and as shown in Figure The SEM study demonstrates that the addition of B4C particles in distinct dimensions and variable proportion of particle sizes in the casting also indicates that the reinforcement of composites in particular can be moderated to 10 percent of B4C owing to the reinforcement of particles in terms of dispersion.

Conclusions

1. The findings show that AMMCs casting by stir casting technique is a cost-effective technique and can be accomplished by using SEM to achieve a uniform distribution of the strengthened particles and homogeneous characteristics.
2. The development of cast Al6061, which has been studied with an rise in the structure of B4C percentage and particle size at distinct dimensions, demonstrates that lower particle size will result in more finished structures compared to big particle sizes.

3. Reinforcement weight proportion is regarded the main parameter for controlling mechanical characteristics.

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